

Supplementary Table 1. 34 representative genes associated with the *HIF1A* pathway and their biological effects.

Angiogenesis	Growth and Survival	Glucose metabolism	Invasion and Metastasis	HIF1A activity	Miscellaneous
<i>VEGFA</i>	<i>EPO</i>	<i>ENO1</i>	<i>KRT19</i>	<i>VHL</i>	<i>CA9</i>
<i>ENG</i>	<i>ADM</i>	<i>SLC2A1 (GLUT1)</i>	<i>VIM</i>	<i>SUMO1</i>	<i>DDIT4</i>
<i>LRP1</i>	<i>IGFBP1</i>	<i>GAPDH</i>	<i>COL5A1</i>	<i>MTOR</i>	<i>PDCD1(PD-1)</i>
	<i>IGFBP2</i>	<i>LDHA</i>	<i>FNI</i>	<i>HGF</i>	<i>CD274(PD-L1)</i>
	<i>IGFBP3</i>	<i>HK1</i>		<i>MET</i>	
	<i>TGFA</i>	<i>HK2</i>		<i>BICD1</i>	
	<i>TGFB3</i>	<i>ALDOA</i>			
	<i>TGFB1</i>				
	<i>NOS2</i>				
	<i>IGF2</i>				
	<i>PGK1</i>				
	<i>PDGFB</i>				
	<i>CXCR4</i>				

Supplementary Table 2. Correlations of *BICD1* expression with the clinicopathological features of patients in the TCGA LGG cohort

Clinicopathological feature	<i>n</i> (%)	<i>BICD1</i> expression, <i>n</i> (%)		<i>p</i>
	508 (100)	Low, <i>n</i> =254 (50.0)	High, <i>n</i> =254 (50.0)	
<i>IDH1</i> status				2.235×10 ⁻¹²
Mutant	394 (77.6)	230 (58.4)	164 (41.6)	
Wild-type	114 (22.4)	24 (21.1)	90 (78.9)	
Overall survival indicator				2.649×10 ⁻¹⁰
0 (alive)	385 (75.8)	223 (57.9)	162 (42.1)	
1 (dead)	123 (24.2)	31 (25.2)	92 (74.8)	
<i>ATRX</i> status				4.015×10 ⁻⁸
Mutant	192 (37.8)	126 (65.6)	66 (34.4)	
Wild-type	316 (62.2)	128 (40.5)	188 (59.5)	
WHO Grade				6.085×10 ⁻⁸
Grade II	245 (48.2)	153 (62.4)	92 (37.6)	
Grade III	263 (51.8)	101 (38.4)	162 (61.6)	
<i>TP53</i> status				9.997×10 ⁻⁸
Mutant	246 (48.4)	153 (62.2)	93 (37.8)	
Wild-type	262 (51.6)	101 (38.5)	161 (61.5)	
<i>EGFR</i> status				0.000012
Wild-type	473 (93.1)	249 (52.6)	224 (47.4)	
Mutant	35 (6.9)	5 (14.3)	30 (85.7)	
Age at initial diagnosis				0.003402
≤40	249 (49.0)	141 (56.6)	108 (43.4)	
>40	259 (51.0)	113 (43.6)	146 (56.4)	
1p19q copy number				0.398106
Codeleted	171 (33.7)	81 (47.4)	90 (52.6)	
Others	337 (66.3)	173 (51.3)	164 (48.7)	
Histological type				0.854793
Others	316 (62.2)	159 (50.3)	157 (49.7)	
Astrocytoma	192 (37.8)	95 (49.5)	97 (50.5)	
Gender				0.858284
Female	226 (44.5)	112 (49.6)	114 (50.4)	
Male	282 (55.5)	142 (50.4)	140 (49.6)	

Supplementary Table 3. Correlations of the KPS with *BICD1* expression and the clinicopathological features of patients in the TCGA LGG cohort

Clinicopathological features	<i>n</i>	KPS (range: 40~100), <i>n</i> (%)		<i>p</i>
	300	>80, 197 (65.7)	≤80, 103 (34.3)	
<i>IDH1</i> status				0.000148
Mutant	233	166 (71.2)	67 (28.8)	
Wild-type	67	31 (46.3)	36 (53.7)	
<i>EGFR</i> status				0.002639
Wild-type	278	189 (68.0)	89 (32.0)	
Mutant	22	8 (36.4)	14 (63.6)	
<i>BICD1</i> expression				0.005164
Low	150	110 (73.3)	40 (26.7)	
High	150	87 (58.0)	63 (42.0)	
Overall survival indicator				0.018944
0 (alive)	212	148 (69.8)	64 (30.2)	
1 (dead)	88	49 (55.7)	39 (44.3)	
Age (at initial diagnosis)				0.071784
≤40	138	98 (71.0)	40 (29.0)	
>40	162	99 (61.1)	63 (38.9)	
<i>TP53</i> status				0.096064
Mutant	151	106 (70.2)	45 (29.8)	
Wild-type	149	91 (61.1)	58 (38.9)	
WHO grade				0.102078
Grade II	136	96 (70.6)	40 (29.4)	
Grade III	164	101 (61.6)	63 (38.4)	
1p19q copy number				0.344430
Codeleted	98	68 (69.4)	30 (30.6)	
Others	202	129 (63.9)	73 (36.1)	
<i>ATRX</i> status				0.477685
Mutant	119	81 (68.1)	38 (31.9)	
Wild-type	181	116 (64.1)	65 (35.9)	
Gender				0.963789
Female	148	97 (65.5)	51 (34.5)	
Male	152	100 (65.8)	52 (34.2)	

KPS: Karnofsky Performance Score

Supplementary Table 4. Univariate Cox's regression analysis for comparing the prognostic significance between *BICD1* expression and the clinicopathological features of patients in the TCGA LGG cohort.

Variables	Subgroups	Univariate		
		HR	95% CI	<i>p</i>
<i>EGFR</i> status	Mutant (<i>n</i> =35) vs. Wild-type (<i>n</i> =473)	5.162	3.238-8.228	5.215×10⁻¹²
<i>IDH1</i> status	Wild-type (<i>n</i> =114) vs. Mutant (<i>n</i> =394)	4.445	3.085-6.405	1.205×10⁻¹⁵
WHO grade	G3 (<i>n</i> =263) vs. G2 (<i>n</i> =245)	3.314	2.231-4.922	2.960×10⁻⁹
Age	>40 (<i>n</i> =259) vs. ≤40 (<i>n</i> =249)	2.889	1.964-4.249	7.057×10⁻⁸
<i>BICD1</i> expression	High (<i>n</i> =254) vs. Low (<i>n</i> =254)	2.731	1.814-4.113	0.000002
1p19q copy number	Others (<i>n</i> =337) vs. Codeleted (<i>n</i> =171)	2.602	1.626-4.165	0.000067
<i>TP53</i> status	Wild-type (<i>n</i> =262) vs. Mutant (<i>n</i> =246)	1.422	0.996-2.030	0.052633
<i>ATRX</i> status	Wild-type (<i>n</i> =316) vs. Mutant (<i>n</i> =192)	1.408	0.975-2.034	0.067904
Gender	Male (<i>n</i> =282) vs. Female (<i>n</i> =226)	1.060	0.741-1.516	0.750157

HR: hazard ratio, CI: confidence interval

Supplementary Table 5. Multivariate Cox's regression analysis for comparing the prognostic significance between *BICD1* expression and the clinicopathological features of patients in the TCGA LGG cohort.

Variables	Subgroups	Multivariate		
		Adjusted HR	95% CI	<i>p</i>
1p19q copy number	Others (<i>n</i> =337) vs. Codeleted (<i>n</i> =171)	3.787	2.005-7.154	0.000041
Age	>40 (<i>n</i> =259) vs. ≤40 (<i>n</i> =249)	2.673	1.726-4.140	0.000011
WHO grade	G3 (<i>n</i> =263) vs. G2 (<i>n</i> =245)	2.201	1.430-3.387	0.000335
<i>BICD1</i> expression	High (<i>n</i> =254) vs. Low (<i>n</i> =254)	1.896	1.219-2.950	0.004547
<i>IDH1</i> status	Wild-type (<i>n</i> =114) vs. Mutant (<i>n</i> =394)	1.687	0	0.086014
<i>TP53</i> status	Wild-type (<i>n</i> =262) vs. Mutant (<i>n</i> =246)	1.601	0.824-3.110	0.164745
Gender	Male (<i>n</i> =282) vs. Female (<i>n</i> =226)	1.384	0	0.088048
<i>ATRX</i> status	Wild-type (<i>n</i> =316) vs. Mutant (<i>n</i> =192)	1.141	0	0.672265
<i>EGFR</i> status	Mutant (<i>n</i> =35) vs. Wild-type (<i>n</i> =473)	1.054	0	0.857723

HR: hazard ratio, CI: confidence interval

Supplementary Figure 1. The prognostic significance of *HIF1A* expression in the TCGA LGG cohort.